

Nachhaltiger Umgang mit Forschungssoftware

Prof. Dr. Konrad U. Förstner

Auftaktveranstaltung für den
Zertifikatskurs Forschungsdatenmanagement 2022/2023

02.09.2022

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7043911>

Wissenschaft \Leftrightarrow Technologie

Software – ein ubiquitäres Werkzeug der Wissenschaft

Bisher wird die Relevanz von Software nicht ausreichend gewürdigt.
Ein Kulturwandel ist nötig.

```
In [1]: import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sns
```

```
In [2]: table_file = "Expression_comparison.csv"
comparisons = pd.read_csv(table_file, sep="\t", comment="#")
comparisons.set_index('Gene', inplace=True)
```

```
In [3]: %matplotlib inline
```

```
In [4]: ax = sns.clustermap(comparisons, cmap="YlGnBu")
```


Genomic analysis of elongated skulls reveals extensive female-biased immigration to Early Medieval Bavaria

Krishna R. Veeramah^a, Andreas Rott^{b,1}, Melanie Groß^{c,1}, Lucy van Dorp^d, Saioa López^e, Karola Kirsanow^c, Christian Sell^c, Jens Blöcher^c, Daniel Wegmann^{f,g}, Vivian Link^{f,g}, Zuzana Hofmanová^{f,g}, Joris Peters^{b,h}, Bernd Trautmann^b, Anja Gairhosⁱ, Jochen Haberstrohⁱ, Bernd Paffgen^k, Garrett Hellenthal^d, Brigitte Haas-Gebhard^l, Michaela Harbeck^{b,2,3}, and Joachim Burger^{c,2,3}

^aDepartment of Ecology and Evolution, Stony Brook University, Stony Brook, NY 11794-5245; ^bState Collection for Anthropology and Palaeoanatomy, Bavarian Natural History Collections, 80333 Munich, Germany; ^cPalaeogenetics Group, Institute of Organismic and Molecular Evolution, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, 55099 Mainz, Germany; ^dUCL Genetics Institute, Department of Genetics, Evolution and Environment, University College London, WC1E 6BT London, United Kingdom; ^eUCL Genetics Institute, Department of Genetics, Evolution and Environment, University College London, WC1E 6DD London, United Kingdom; ^fDepartment of Biology, University of Fribourg, 1700 Fribourg, Switzerland; ^gDepartment of Biology, University of Fribourg, 1700 Fribourg, Switzerland; ^hArchaeoBioCenter and Institute for Palaeoanatomy, Domestikation Research and the History of Veterinary Medicine, Ludwig Maximilian University, 80539 Munich, Germany; ⁱBavarian State Archaeological Collection, 80538 Munich, Germany; ^jBavarian State Department of Monuments and Sites, 80539 Munich, Germany; and ^kInstitute of Prehistoric and Protohistoric Archaeology, Ludwig Maximilian University, 80799 Munich, Germany

The Scientific Paper Is Obsolete

Here's what's next:

Edited by Eske Willerslev, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark, and approved January 30, 2018 (received for review November 21, 2017)
<https://www.theatlantic.com/science/archive/2018/04/the-scientific-paper-is-obsolete/556676/>
Modern European genetic structure demonstrates strong correlation to form in the 5th century AD, and that it emanated from a com-

- NCBI Home
- Resource List (A-Z)
- All Resources
- Chemicals & Bioassays
- Data & Software
- DNA & RNA
- Domains & Structures
- Genes & Expression
- Genetics & Medicine
- Genomes & Maps
- Homology
- Literature
- Proteins
- Sequence Analysis
- Taxonomy
- Training & Tutorials
- Variation

Welcome to NCBI

The National Center for Biotechnology Information advances science and health by providing access to biomedical and genomic information.

[About the NCBI](#) | [Mission](#) | [Organization](#) | [NCBI News & Blog](#)

Submit

Deposit data or manuscripts into NCBI databases

Download

Transfer NCBI data to your computer

Learn

Find help documents, attend a class or watch a tutorial

Develop

Use NCBI APIs and code libraries to build applications

Analyze

Identify an NCBI tool for your data analysis task

Research

Explore NCBI research and collaborative projects

Popular Resources

- PubMed
- Bookshelf
- PubMed Central
- BLAST
- Nucleotide
- Genome
- SNP
- Gene
- Protein
- PubChem

NCBI News & Blog

New publication on AMRFinder, a resistance genes in pathogen gen

Read the recent publication (PMID AMRFinder, a tool that identifies a resistance (AMR) genes in bacter

NCBI at ASHG 2019: Two Data C How to Analyze NextGen Sequen Genetic Variation Population Data

NCBI will be attending the Americ Genetics (ASHG) 2019 in Housto

dbSNP celebrates 20 years!

dbSNP was established in August collaboration between NCBI and t Genome Research Institute (NHG small scale nucleotide variants. Th both common and rare single base

A glass sphere sits atop the base of a light bulb, which is placed on an open book. The sphere reflects the surrounding environment, including the book and the light bulb. The book's pages are filled with text, and the light bulb's base is white and cylindrical.

Software ist nicht nur ein Werkzeug, sondern auch ein Ergebnis wissenschaftlichen Arbeitens – Qualität, Zugang und Zitierbarkeit müssen/müssten gewährleistet sein.

Software \neq Daten

Software kann Infrastruktur sein.

Im Kontext wissenschaftlicher Software gibt es viele offene Fragen.

Generell muss geklärt werden, was hierbei gute wissenschaftlicher Praxis ist.

Wie können wir Software möglichst FAIR* und Open machen?

*Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable

Wie sorgen wir für gute Qualität/Validität von Software?

Wo ist welcher Aufwand angemessen / notwendig?

POLICY —

Microsoft Excel: The ruiner of global economies?

A paper used to justify austerity economics appears to contain an Excel error.

ARS STAFF - 4/17/2013, 12:20 AM

<https://arstechnica.com/tech-policy/2013/04/microsoft-excel-the-ruiner-of-global-economies/>

Gene name errors: Lessons not learned

Mandhri Abeysooriya, Megan Soria, Mary Sravya Kasu, Mark Ziemann

Version 2

Published: July 30, 2021 • <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008984>

Article

Authors

Metrics

Comments

Media Coverage

Peer Review

Abstract

Author summary

Background

Results

Discussion

Methods

Supporting information

Acknowledgments

Abstract

Erroneous conversion of gene names into other dates and other data types has been a frustration for computational biologists for years. We hypothesized that such errors in supplementary files might diminish after a report in 2016 highlighting the extent of the problem. To assess this, we performed a scan of supplementary files published in PubMed Central from 2014 to 2020. Overall, gene name errors continued to accumulate unabated in the period after 2016. An improved scanning software we developed identified gene name errors in 30.9% (3,436/11,117) of <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008984> higher than previously estimated. This is due to gene names being converted not just to dates

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008984>

Cluster failure: Why fMRI inferences for spatial extent have inflated false-positive rates.

Eklund A¹, Nichols TE², Knutsson H³.

Author information

Erratum in

Correction for Eklund et al., Cluster failure: Why fMRI inferences for spatial extent have inflated false-positive rates. [Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A. 2016]

Abstract

The most widely used task functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) analyses use parametric statistical methods that depend on a variety of assumptions. In this work, we use real resting-state data and a total of 3 million random task group analyses to compute empirical familywise error rates for the fMRI software packages SPM, FSL, and AFNI, as well as a nonparametric permutation method. For a nominal familywise error rate of 5%, the parametric statistical methods are shown to be conservative for voxelwise inference and invalid for clusterwise inference. Our results suggest that the principal cause of the invalid cluster inferences is spatial autocorrelation functions that do not follow the assumed Gaussian shape. By comparison, the nonparametric permutation test is found to produce nominal results for voxelwise as well as clusterwise inference. These findings speak to the need of validating the statistical methods being used in the field of neuroimaging.

Wie sollte Software publiziert werden?

Referencing and citing content

You can use third-party tools to cite and reference content on GitHub.

In this article

Issuing a persistent identifier for your repository with Zenodo

Publicizing and citing research material with Figshare

Issuing a persistent identifier for your repository with Zenodo

To make your repositories easier to reference in academic literature, you can create persistent identifiers, also known as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs). You can use the data archiving tool [Zenodo](#) to archive a repository on GitHub.com and issue a DOI for the archive.

Tips:

- Zenodo can only access public repositories, so make sure the repository you want to archive is [public](#).
- If you want to archive a repository that belongs to an organization, the organization owner may need to [approve access](#) for the Zenodo application.

Wie kann Software zitiert werden?

⌚ 4 minute read

What is a CITATION.cff file?

`CITATION.cff` files are plain text files with human- and machine-readable citation information for software (and datasets). Code developers can include them in their repositories to let others know how to correctly cite their software.

This is an example of a simple `CITATION.cff` file:

```
cff-version: 1.2.0
message: "If you use this software, please cite it as below."
authors:
  - family-names: Druskat
    given-names: Stephan
    orcid: https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4925-7248
title: "My Research Software"
version: 2.0.4
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.1234
date-released: 2021-08-11
```

The format of `CITATION.cff` files is the **Citation File Format (CFF)**.

<https://citation-file-format.github.io/>

ON THIS PAGE

[WHAT IS A CITATION.CFF FILE?](#)[WHY YOU SHOULD ADD A CITATION.CFF FILE TO YOUR REPOSITORY!](#)[SUPPORTED BY GITHUB](#)[SUPPORTED BY ZENODO](#)[SUPPORTED BY ZOTERO](#)[CREATE A CITATION.CFF FILE NOW!](#)[TOOLS FOR WORKING WITH CITATION.CFF FILES](#)[HAVE AN IDEA? FOUND A PROBLEM?](#)

Wie kann ich für die langfristige Verfügbarkeit von Software sorgen?

Software is fragile

unlike words carved in stone it can
be deleted or get corrupted

We are building the universal software archive

Collect
Preserve
Share

We **collect** and **preserve** software in source code form, because software embodies our technical and scientific knowledge and humanity cannot afford the risk of losing it.

Software is a precious part of our cultural heritage. We curate and make accessible all the software we collect, because only by **sharing** it we can guarantee its preservation in the very long term.

[Discover our mission](#)

Wie finde ich Software?

Wie kann man Software als Forschungsleistung bewerten?

A collection of old, worn tools including hammers, pliers, a saw, and gloves, arranged on a dark wooden surface. The tools are arranged in a somewhat organized manner, with some hammers and pliers in the foreground and others in the background. The lighting is dramatic, with strong shadows and highlights, suggesting a workshop or a rustic setting. A semi-transparent white banner is overlaid across the middle of the image, containing the text "Welche (neuen) Berufe und Karrierewege benötigen wir?".

Welche (neuen) Berufe und Karrierewege benötigen wir?

Wie muss die Ausbildung/Lehre angepasst werden?

Welche juristischen Aspekte sind zu beachten?

A woman with long blonde hair, wearing a blue shirt and a watch, is sitting at a wooden table in a cafe or office setting. She is writing in a spiral notebook with a black pen. On the table, there is a white coffee cup on a saucer, another notebook, and a pen. The background is softly blurred, showing other people and interior lights.

Mittlerweile gibt es zahlreiche nationale und internationale Organisationen und Initiativen zu dem Thema Forschungssoftware.

Eine Auswahl:

- Software Carpentry (1998)
- Software Sustainability Institute (2008)
- Task Group Forschungssoftware organisiert Workshop "Access to and reuse of scientific software" (2016)
- de-RSE e.V. (2016)
- Allianz-AG "Digitale Werkzeuge: Software und Services" (2016)
- DFG call "Research Software Sustainability" (2016)
- Positionspapier der Free Software Foundation Europe zum Thema Forschungsdaten (2017)
- US Research Software Sustainability Institute (2018)

Recommendations on the

Development, Use and Provision of Research Software

Research Software Working Group
in the Priority Initiative Digital Information
of the Alliance of German Science Organisations

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1172988>

Leitlinien zur Sicherung guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis

Kodex

DFG

https://www.dfg.de/foerderung/grundlagen_rahmenbedingungen/gwp/

Recognising the Importance of Software in Research – Research Software Engineers (RSEs), a UK Example

Open Science Monitor Case Study

Jon Switters, David Osimo
January - 2019

Research and
Innovation

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/importance_of_software_in_research.pdf

Home » Browse » An environment for sustainable research software in Germany and beyond:...

OPINION ARTICLE

REVISED An environment for sustainable research software in Germany and beyond: current state, open challenges, and call for action [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]

Hartwig Anzt^{1,2*}, Felix Bach ^{3-5*}, Frank Löffler^{3,6*},
^{8*},
 Alexander Struck ¹⁰, Franziska Appel¹¹,
 Michael Bader⁹, Lutz Bruschi ⁹,
 Piotr Wojciech Dabrowski ¹⁷,
 Bernadette Fritzsche¹⁸, Maximilian D. Funk¹⁹, Volker Gast³, Florian Goth²⁰, Jean-Noël Grad ¹⁶,
 Jan Hegewald ¹⁸, Sibylle Hermann¹⁶, Florian Hohmann²¹, Stephan Janosch²²,
 Dominik Kutra ²⁶,
 Fabian Rack²⁷, Fabian H.C. Raters ¹⁶,
 Malte Reißig ³³,
 Jan P. Thiele ³⁵, Stefan Unger³⁶, Rudolf Weeber¹⁶

* Equal contributors

 Author details

ALL METRICS

5792

VIEWS

624

DOWNLOADS

Get PDF

Get XML

Cite

Export

Track

Email

Share

Open Peer Review

Reviewer Status

Reviewer Reports

	Invited Reviewers	
	1	2
Version 2 (revision) 26 Jan 21	 read	
Version 1 27 Apr 20	 read	

1. **Willi Hasselbring** , Kiel University, Kiel, Germany
2. **Radovan Bast** , UIT The Arctic University of Norway, Tromsø, Norway

Fazit

- Mit der rapide wachsenden Menge an Forschungsdaten steigt die Relevanz von Forschungssoftware
- In Bezug auf Forschungssoftware ist ein großer Umbruch in den letzten Jahren geschehen
- Weiterhin sind viele Fragen offen
- Kulturwandel und Diskussion ist notwendig

Vielen Dank.

Welche Fragen haben Sie?

foerstner@zbmed.de

@konradfoerstner / @zb_med

<https://www.zbmed.de/>